

Learning-based Clustering Method for Semantic Place Retrieval

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Introduction

- Knowledge graph (KG) usually consists of entities and relationships that connect them. Besides, they have been enriched to incorporate the spatial and temporal information, which make it possible for more sophisticated search and analysis.
- In this work, we focus on the top-k relevant semantic place retrieval (kSP) problem which combines keyword search with location retrieval. The goal is to build top-k minimum weight subtrees, called semantic places.
- In this work, we consider using clustering method to reduce the size of retrieval space, so as to avoid conducting an online graph traversal on large-scale KGs. We propose a Learning-based Semantic Place Clustering (LSPC) method for semantic place retrieval problem.

Evaluation

Data and Training Set

- Experiments are carried out on a 3.4 GHz quad-core machine with Ubuntu 16.04 and 32G of memory, and the algorithm is implemented in Java. We use two datasets to demonstrate our experimental results: YAGO2 and DBpedia. The specific information of the datasets we use is shown in Table 1. All data represents the number of individual elements.

Table 1 Statistics of experimental datasets

Dataset	Entities	Spatial Entities	Keywords
YAGO2	9,800,000	4,770,000	3,700,000
DBpedia	2,600,000	880,000	2,900,000

- We randomly selected 35,000 places in the dataset as training samples.

Efficiency Evaluation of SSPR-DC

- This experiment tests the performance of SSPR-DC in terms of retrieval time by changing the number of clusters n and returned results k .

Figure 2. Retrieval time of SSPR-DC under different parameters

- As shown in Figure 2, regardless of the number of returned results k , with the number of clusters n increases, the speed shows a rapid boost at first, and then a slow recovery. Because with a sufficient number of n , the places have already been well separated. Further increases of n will increase scanning costs. With k increases, the retrieval time will increase too. Because the more k , the more clusters need to be traversed. We also empirically observed that setting the number of clusters to approximately 0.5% of total number will minimize retrieval time.

Algorithm

Overall Framework

- Figure 1 presents the overall framework of our method, which can be divided into three stages: encoding, clustering and retrieval.

Figure 1. The overall framework of our work

- In the encoding stage, we design a **spatial entity encoder**, encoding the spatial and semantic information of each spatial entity into one embedding vector.
- In the clustering stage, we use a **cascaded siamese network** framework to divide spatial entities with similar characteristics into the same cluster.
- In the retrieval stage, we use the SSPR method as a downstream task to evaluate the efficiency impact of our method on retrieval.

Spatial Entity Encoding

- Given a set of spatial entities $S = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\}$, each entity $s_i = (x_i, y_i)$ is composed of an 2-dimensional coordinate $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^L$ and a keyword set $y_i \in \mathbb{R}^E$.
- The Spatial Entity Encoder can be defined as $Enc^S(s): \mathbb{R}^{L+E} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$. Using this function, the spatial entity can be mapped to a D-dimensional representation vector. \mathbb{R}^{L+E} indicates that the encoding is a combination of coordinate and semantic. as $Enc^S(s)$ indicates that they may depend on other entities in the set S .

- We design two encoders to encode the information of spatial entities, namely spatial and semantic encoder.
- The spatial encoder is defined as $Enc^x = NN(PE^t(x))$, in which $NN()$ represents fully connected ReLU layer, $PE^t(x)$ represents multiscale representation of concatenated vectors.
- The semantic encoder $Enc^y()$ encodes keyword embedding set into a semantic embedding vector $e[y_i] \in \mathbb{R}^{d(y)}$. We obtain such embedding vector for each entity by calculating mean of the keyword vectors in keyword embedding set, as shown below:

$$e[y_i] = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H t_h^{(y)}$$

- $t_h^{(y)}$ represents h-th keyword vector in keyword embedding set, and H represents the total number of vectors.

Cascaded Siamese Network

- We formalize the semantic place clustering as an optimization problem, with the goal of maximizing the similarity of places in same cluster. Specifically, we design a Clustering Partitioning Objective (CPO) as below:

$$CPO = \sum_{c=1}^n \sum_{s_i \in C_c} \sum_{s_j \in C_c} (1 - S(s_i, s_j))$$

- $S(s_i, s_j)$ represents similarity of a pair of places within the same cluster. By minimizing CPO, semantic places' differences in the same cluster can be minimized, while in different clusters are maximized.
- We propose a learning framework composed of cascaded siamese networks to speed up training time. This framework divides place set in a hierarchical manner from large to small, with each network responsible for dividing a cluster into two sub clusters, continuously refining the clustering results.

Comparison with kSP and SSPR

- This experiment aims to compare the performance of kSP, SSPR and SSPR-DC, evaluating 100 queries by changing the number of returned results k .

Figure 3. Retrieval time of three methods

- As shown in Figure 3, The results show that on DBpedia, the retrieval speed of SSPR-DC is 3.8-8.1 times that of kSP and 1.5-3.9 times that of SSPR; On YAGO2, this speed is 3.8-10 times that of kSP and 1.8-7.2 times that of SSPR. This indicates that SSPR-DC indeed improves retrieval speed compared to kSP and SSPR methods, as SSPR-DC can more efficiently prune clusters that do not meet queries.

Conclusion

- We propose a learning-based clustering method for semantic place retrieval, to address the challenge of extensive retrieval space in traditional method. However, since various clustering methods can yield diverse results, solely focusing on execution time may overlook important aspects like accuracy or relevancy. Therefore, our next step in the study will consider if varying cluster results could lead to different kSP outcomes, ensuring a more balanced and thorough evaluation.

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